

MANAGEMENT OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

¹Sh.K. Mardonov, ²F.Sh. Mardonov

¹Professor head of department of UzNIIPN

²Undergraduate of Chirchik SPU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7625929>

Abstract. *The article deals with the methodological training of leaders in continuous education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the existing shortcomings in this area and ways to eliminate them through modern pedagogical theories, educational technologies*

Keywords: *continuous education, director, school management, attitude, communication, teacher, education process, social activity, development dynamics.*

It is known that the issue of development of scientific-methodical training of managers who have been consistently operating in the management of the continuous education system in the process of social-economic, spiritual-educational updates, developing market economy relations, progress in the field of science, technology and information globalization in the Republic of Uzbekistan is among the current problems.

It requires the necessity of radical improvement of state programs, government decisions adopted in order to create the necessary conditions for the participants of the reform process aimed at the development of the continuous education system and to improve the quality and efficiency of education, activities of general secondary school leaders, finding positive solutions to existing problems, innovative approaches to the organization and management of pedagogical processes, and the implementation of modern pedagogical technologies.

Taking into account the social order placed before the continuous education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the existing shortcomings in the methodological training of the leading personnel can be eliminated by retraining and improving their skills and organizing independent work on them, and there is also a need to arm them with modern pedagogical theories and educational technologies.

The analysis of existing literature shows that in the conditions of today's globalization, there are a number of deficiencies in the management of general secondary educational institutions on scientific and methodological bases, which are:

- lack of completeness of continuity between the stages of continuous education;
- professional, scientific-methodical preparation and potential of the leading personnel lag behind the content of education and its methodological support;
- social and creative activity, political-ideological maturity of the majority of school leaders is not at the required level;
- insufficient theoretical and methodological basis of the training system for the heads of general secondary schools, as well as lack of attention to acquisition of methodical knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the use of modern information and pedagogical technologies in this process, etc.

Therefore, the fundamental improvement of the activities of general secondary school leaders requires the effective implementation of the following tasks in order to create the necessary conditions and opportunities for teachers and students:

- planning of activity and determining its effectiveness in advance;

- defining the goal correctly and clarify the directions for its achievement;
- choosing directions for the implementation of tasks set on the way to achieving the goal;
- following the principle of collegiality in making decisions;
- distribution of tasks according to the possibilities, abilities and essence of tasks of pedagogical staff;
- creation of necessary conditions for continuous professional development of teaching staff;
- providing teachers with the necessary material and technical and modern scientific and methodical products;
- organization, management, quality and efficiency of pedagogical processes;
- ensuring the integrity and continuity of pedagogical processes based on the coordination of educational relations;
- study the needs and inclinations of the participants of the pedagogical process and coordinate their activities;
- implementation of advanced pedagogical experience and modern information and pedagogical technologies;
- application of SES and qualification in practice and its monitoring;
- collection and analysis of information on the dynamics of development of general secondary education;
- control of the timely execution of decisions and orders, etc.

Organization of the educational process in educational institutions and its improvement, as well as the development of leadership activities, based on the principles of the state education policy defined in the national program of the state, are among the priority tasks.

If we pay attention to the essence and direction of these tasks in the organization of the activity of the educational institution, the performance of these tasks belongs not only to a specific head of the general secondary educational institution - the director or the deputy director, but also the performance of these tasks is required to be carried out by all the leaders and official employees of the general secondary educational institution.

Ensuring the implementation of the specified tasks represents the management activities including planning, organization, control and analysis, objective evaluation - organization and coordination of the activities of the pedagogic staff in order to achieve the intended results. This, in turn, confirms that management activity and its effectiveness are not only related to the activity of the school director, but also to the activity of all managers, pedagogical staff and specialists of the general secondary educational institution.

When we analyze the literature, we see different interpretations of management:

According to Prof. U.I. Inoyatov, it differs according to the level and directions of management of the educational system. In particular, 1) according to the level - internal management of state, inter-branch, network, local and general education schools; 2) according to directions - organizational, systematic, meaningful, from the point of view of personnel issues and methodical [1, 11-p.].

According to Acad.R.H.Djuraev and Prof.S.T.Turgunov, school management is a cooperative activity of leaders and pedagogues, is considered to be scientific-based activity oriented on organizing and managing the educational process on a scientific basis, coordinating the activities of the participants of this process and providing students with in-depth knowledge of

subjects and moral education, guidance of career choice and education of a well-rounded person [2, 23-p.].

According to the approach of the researcher M.Mirkosimov, management first of all implies the economic and material condition of people, their social activities, their upbringing in the spirit of our values, if there is no organization, order, division of labor in the team, if the role and tasks of the person in the team are not determined, then there cannot be a labor team. Naturally, work cannot be carried out without management, without establishing and supporting a certain order [3, 14-15-p.].

It is emphasized to carry out the leadership and management of general education schools in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan on public education, self-management of the team by the school board (council of pedagogues) and the importance of the Regulation approved by the direct supervisor in the management process, management of the educational process by the director of the educational institution in accordance with the requirements of this Regulation, the establishment of the school pedagogic council, the team uniting the pedagogic staff in order to develop and improve the educational process, to develop the professional skills and creativity of teachers and educators, , as well as the establishment of the work order of the pedagogic council in the school regulations [4, 14-15-p.].

French scientist A. Fayol, one of the founders of management theory, who made a significant contribution to the development of management science, saw management as the future; called it a powerful weapon that manages the organization; organizes the activity; coordinates the activity; controls the execution of decisions and orders.

Management is a choice that requires a specific art and skill, making decisions based on that choice or pursuit, and controlling its implementation [5, 6-p.].

Management is managing and working with people [38].

"Management is an active influence on a management system or an object to achieve a specific goal", and "management is the influence of one system on another, a person on another person or a certain person on a group of people" [6, 126-p].

Therefore, planning, organizing, controlling and coordinating the activities of subjects in the organization of pedagogical processes in general secondary educational institutions, ensuring their quality and efficiency on the basis of objective evaluation and encouragement represent the management activities of leaders.

The goal set before educational institutions is emphasized as the main criterion determining the need to organize management activities, represents setting tasks to achieve the goal, pre-planning the activities to be organized, choosing the directions of implementation, distributing the tasks that must be performed, coordinating the activities of the participants in the process organized to achieve the goal, management activities , its implementation functions, implementation consistency, management algorithm, implementation directions, management methods, ways of management of organizing and coordinating personnel activities, decisions made in this direction management decisions [2, 23-p.].

The analysis of modern pedagogical processes shows that when setting goals for an educational institution, school leaders should take into account the following requirements:

- the analysis of existing needs and problems in the educational system serves as the main factor in setting goals, taking into account the initial opportunities and means, reserves;
- goals should be relevant enough to solve important problems;

-goals should be complex, but clear, as well as represent the development of the school in the near future;

- the more carefully the goals are formulated, the easier it is to achieve them;

-goals should be diagnostic, motivating, encouraging;

- correspondence of the goals to the school tasks;

- the fact that the goals of cooperation are known to all its subjects and accepted in a way that is understandable for them ensures the coordination of collective activities and goals;

-smaller specific goals should be subordinated to larger and long-term goals and aspirations.

Therefore, in order to prevent accidental and unexpected situations in ensuring and improving the vital activities of general secondary educational institutions, it is important to implement a systematic approach in the implementation of the functional tasks of the heads of educational institutions in the areas of management activity, because in the systematic approach, the heads of general secondary educational institutions are the areas of management activity of the system. as, that is, according to their connection and connection, and according to the content and essence of the directions of management activity, they are imagined as a whole.

REFERENCES

1. Иноятлов У.И. Теоретические и организационно-методические основы управления и контроля качества образования в профессиональном колледже: Дисс. ...д-ра пед.наук. –Тошкент, 2003. -315 с.
2. Джураев Р.Х., Турғунов С.Т. Умумий ўрта таълим муассасаларини бошқаришда менежментнинг асосий тушунчалари. –Тошкент: Фан, 2006. -50 б.
3. Мирқосимов М. Мактабни бошқаришнинг назарий ва педагогик асослари. –Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1995. - 159 б.
4. Йўлдошев Ж.Ф., Усмонов С.А. Таълим менежменти. -Тошкент, 2006.-73 б.
5. Китов А.И. Экспериментальное исследование процесса руководства: социально-психологические проблемы руководства и управления коллективами. –М., 1984. -184 с.
6. Кларин М.В. Инновационные модели обучения в зарубежных педагогических поисках.- М.: Арена, 1994. -222 с.